

Planar graph representation of [60]- and [70]fullerene structures : Some advantages with such representations

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Abstract : A method for stepwise construction of the planar graphs of [60]- and [70]fullerenes maintaining isolation of pentagons and a five-fold rotational axis of symmetry has been explained and the graphs have been utilized to show why these two fullerenes have important distinctive spectroscopic features. The rationale for placing double bonds in the rings and enumeration of the possible isomeric 1,2 addition products ($C_{60}X_4$, $X = H, Br$) have also been explained with the help of the planar graphs.

Keywords : Planar graph, fullerene, electronic structure, Schlegel diagrams.

Introduction

The geometries and electronic structures of [60]- and [70]fullerene molecules are now well established¹⁻³. [60]fullerene molecule contains 12 pentagons and 20 hexagons of carbon atoms fused together as embedding on a sphere like the stitches on the surface of a soccer ball; [70]fullerene molecule has 12 pentagons and 25 hexagons (of carbon atoms) fused and embedded on the surface of an ellipsoid. Combinatorially, there may be a very large number of ways of fusing the pentagons and hexagons for each of these two fullerenes. But in the experimentally stable forms of both the fullerenes (which are now available in the market) the pentagons are all separated by intervening hexagons; this is the so called 'isolated pentagon rule' (IPR) first stated by Kroto⁴. The two fullerenes have the distinctive features which are spectroscopically observed : (a) there is no frequency common to infrared and Raman spectra of [60]fullerene but [70]fullerene exhibits a number of IR-Raman coincidences^{2,5-8} and (b) [60]fullerene shows only one ¹³C NMR signal at about 143 ppm but [70]fullerene shows five distinct ¹³C NMR signals² in the range 130 to 150 ppm. Without considering the details of the ring embeddings on the spherical or ellipsoidal surface it is not possible to explain the above observations; for example, a sphere and an ellipsoid (without any marking on the surface) both have a centre of symmetry but the observation (a) shows that [70]fullerene

does not have it. Three dimensional molecular models are useful in demonstrating such symmetry elements and the number of equivalent C atoms of the two fullerenes. However, the details of the ring embeddings can be more clearly shown by means of planar graphs of the fullerene molecules. The objective of the present article is to show how such graphs can be constructed for the two fullerenes, maintaining isolation of pentagons and a five-fold rotation axis of symmetry (which both the molecules possess), and thence to explain the observations (a) and (b). Placement of double bonds in the ring for enumeration of isomeric 1,2 addition products will also be explained.

Some necessary definitions

Graph : A graph $G = (V, E)$ is defined⁹ as a non-empty set $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_k\}$ of points (called 'vertices') together with a set of 'edges' $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_n\}$ such that each e_i is an unordered pair of vertices (v_r, v_s) of the set V . Graphs are usually represented by diagrams where vertices are denoted by points or small circles and edges by lines joining the concerned vertex pairs. Often, in simple language, such representations themselves are called graphs⁹. For example, G_1 in Fig. 1 is a graph with $V = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and $E = \{(1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4), (4, 1), (2, 5), (3, 5)\}$. It is to be noted here that neither the lengths of the edges nor the angles between them are relevant in graph theory – the edges only bear the infor-

Fig. 1. G_1 , a simple graph; G_2 , a graph equivalent to G_1 ; G_3 , a regular graph of vertex degree 2; G_4 or G_5 , a planar graph and G_6 , a non-planar graph.

mation about the connectivity of the vertices; the edges may be drawn by straight or curved lines. Thus, G_2 of Fig. 1 is the same graph as G_1 . Physically, an edge of a graph means a binary relation existing among the objects which the vertices represent. For example, if the vertices mean the atoms in a molecule and the binary relation means 'bondedness' then the conventionally drawn molecular structure itself is a graph. In the abstract definition of a graph 'an unordered pair of vertices' means that in the diagrammatic representation the end vertices of e_i may be in any order, (v_r, v_s) or (v_s, v_r) . (However, in some applications⁹ the order of the vertex-pair in an edge is required and the order is indicated by an arrow from one vertex to the other in the necessary order; such graphs are called 'digraphs' or 'directed graphs' and will not be needed in the present discussions).

Degree of a vertex : The number of other vertices joined to a given vertex is called its degree. For example, in the graph G_1 (Fig. 1) the vertices 1, 4 and 5 are of degree 2 each, the vertices 2 and 3 have degree 3 each. A 1-degree vertex is called a 'pendant' vertex.

Regular graph : A graph is 'regular' if all its vertices are of the same degree. For example, the H-suppressed molecular graph of benzene showing the carbon atom connectivity is a 2-degree regular graph (G_3 , Fig. 1).

Planar graph : A graph G is called 'planar' if it can be drawn on a plane such that no two of its edges intersect without appearance of a new vertex which G does not contain. The graph G_4 (Fig. 1) which has an edge-crossing can be equivalently drawn as G_5 on the plane of the paper with no edge-crossing; so G_4 (or, G_5) is planar. But G_6 (Fig. 1) can in no way be drawn on this plane avoiding edge-crossing¹⁰ and so it is nonplanar. A detailed discussion of planarity of graphs may be found in Refs. 11,12.

Schlegel diagrams : In 1886 the German mathematician Victor Schlegel introduced a method of projecting a polytope from a d -dimensional space on to a $(d-1)$ -dimensional space. For polyhedra this projection simply means representing the faces and edges of a polyhedron by regions and straight line segments respectively on a plane; such a diagram is called 'Schlegel diagram' of the polyhedron and is the same as its planar graph representation if all the edges of the graph are drawn by straight line segments (see Fig. 2 for a square pyramid and an octahedron).

Fig. 2. Schlegel diagrams of a square pyramid and an octahedron.

Horizontal and vertical placement of edges

With the above background, we may proceed to construct planar graphs (Schlegel diagrams) of the two IPR fullerenes under consideration (to be henceforth denoted by C_{60} and C_{70}). There are algorithms for drawing planar graphs of general fullerenes¹³⁻¹⁶.

However, for the IPR [60]- and [70]fullerenes a simple algorithm is possible that maintains isolation of pentagons and a five-fold rotational axis of symmetry. (This algorithm in an extended form, applicable to general IPR

fullerenes of formula C_{50+10n} and C_{60+12n} (with $n =$ a positive integer) was published earlier¹⁷). For this purpose it is necessary to show 'horizontal' and 'transverse' (or 'vertical') placing of an edge in a 'bay' or 'vee' region, Fig. 3. If the two vertices of an edge are joined to the terminals of a 'bay' or 'vee', it is horizontally placed; if only one vertex is joined to the terminals of a 'bay' or 'vee' it is transversely or vertically placed¹⁷.

Fig. 3. Capping 'bay' and regions with horizontal and transverse (or, vertical) placing of edges.

Construction of the fullerene planar graphs

The following steps are to be followed successively to construct the planar graphs :

- (1) For both the fullerenes (C_{60} and C_{70}) start with the planar graph of C_{10} obtained by attaching a pendant vertex to each of the five vertices of a pentagon, this gives a C_{10} fragment with five 'bay' regions¹⁷ (Scheme 1, Fig. 4).
- (2) Cap each 'bay' region with one horizontal edge to get a C_{20} fragment with five 'vee' regions.
- (3) Cap each newly produced 'vee' region with an edge horizontally thereby producing five new pentagons in a C_{30} fragment with five new 'bay' regions.
- (4) Now cap each newly produced 'bay' region with an edge horizontally to construct a C_{40} fragment with five new 'bay's'.
- (5) Again cap the new 'bay' regions with five horizontal edges to produce a C_{50} fragment.

The word 'fragment' has been used so far because all the vertices in Scheme 1 are not of the same degree. In the fullerenes all the C atoms are of the same valence and

their planar graph should be regular of degree 3 (for each vertex). Hence the final step is as follows (Scheme 2, Fig. 5).

For C_{60} , place five vertical edges in the 'bay' regions of the C_{50} fragment (obtained in Scheme 1) and join one vertex of each vertical (transverse) edge to the terminals of each 'bay' region and close the graph by joining the remaining pendant vertices to each other; this will produce five hexagons and six pentagons. The planar graph (Schlegel diagram) of C_{60} with all vertices of degree three is thus constructed. Important to be noted here is that there is no pentagon-pentagon ring fusion.

To construct the C_{70} planar graph repeat steps on the C_{50} fragment of Scheme 1 to get a C_{60} fragment with five 'bay' regions; the outer vertices are still of degree two. So, finally cap each new 'bay' region with a transverse edge to get the regular planar graph of C_{70} fullerene where isolation of pentagons is again evident. It is to be noted here that although graphs do not bear the metric properties (lengths, angles etc.) of the real objects the construction described here preserves at least one five-fold axis of rotational symmetry through the use of pentagons in the Schlegel diagrams.

Explanation of the important features of the two fullerenes using their planar graphs

Infrared-Raman coincidence : The fullerene structure may be thought of as being covered with a net made of rubber string such that the knots are at the C-atoms and the strings between knots are just along the C-C bonds. Let us now stretch the network without tearing such that one pentagon is the outermost, all other pentagons and hexagons are inside, and no two string segments intersect except at the knots. If the resulting stretched network is placed on a plane, the figure becomes the planar graph (Schlegel diagram) of the fullerene. It is found in the [60]fullerene network (Fig. 5) that the pentagons on the two sides of any diameter (for example, the central and outermost pentagons of the [60]fullerene planar graph) are arranged in a staggered manner. This, together with spherical symmetry, causes the [60]fullerene structure to have a centre of inversion. Hence there is no common frequency in the infrared and Raman spectra of [60]fullerene. On the other hand, the planar graph of [70]fullerene at the two ends of any diameter are in eclipsed

Fig. 4. Scheme 1 : Building up C_{50} fragment starting from the C_{10} fragment according to the present algorithm.

orientation, thereby prohibiting a centre of inversion. Hence infrared-Raman coincidence is possible for [70]fullerene. (This is reminiscent of the staggered and eclipsed conformations of the ferrocene complex).

^{13}C NMR signal : Each of the vertices of the [60]fullerene graph (Fig. 5) is at the intersection of two

hexagons and one pentagon. Again, each of the twelve pentagons has five such vertices. Hence all the sixty vertices are graph theoretically equivalent; this, together with spherical symmetry of the molecule causes the sixty carbon atoms to be in the same environment. The single ^{13}C NMR signal of [60]fullerene is thus explained.

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Fig. 5. Scheme 2 : Completing the C₆₀ and C₇₀ planar graphs starting from the C₅₀ fragment according to the present algorithm.

In the planar graph of [70]fullerene all the 70 vertices are not of the same type. There are 60 vertices (for the 12 pentagons) each of which are at the intersection of two

hexagons and one pentagon but there are ten more vertices each at the intersection of three hexagons. The ellipsoidal molecule can be clearly divided into two equal halves by

an equator consisting of ten carbon atoms; in the planar graph (Fig. 5) the corresponding vertices are coloured black. The innermost and outermost pentagons of the planar graph have the same orientation and correspond to the two polar caps of [70]fullerene. The vertices in each of these poles are coloured brown. In between the polar cap and equator, there are three sets of vertices in each half. The first set below (or above) the polar cap contains five vertices (coloured green) directly attached to the vertices of the poles. The second set in each half contains ten vertices (coloured yellow) at the hexagon-hexagon ring fusions. The third set in each half contains ten vertices (coloured red) at the pentagon-hexagon ring fusions. Considering these poles and sets, the carbon atom counts with different chemical environments in C_{70} are as follows :

Pole	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Equator
5×2	5×2	10×2	10×2	10
(Brown)	(Green)	(Yellow)	(Red)	(Black)

This explains the five ^{13}C NMR signals of [70]fullerene in the intensity ratio 1 : 1 : 2 : 2 : 1 as observed experimentally².

Fig. 6. Equator of the C_{70} graph (black vertices), polar caps (innermost and outermost pentagons, brown vertices), Set 1 in each half (five vertices directly attached to the pentagon, marked green), Set 2 in each half (five vertices at the hexagon-hexagon ring fusions, marked yellow), and Set 3 in each half (five vertices at the pentagon-pentagon ring fusions, marked red).

Number of isomeric 1,2 addition products of C_{60}

Studies on addition reactions¹⁸ of [60]fullerene show that in the most dominant canonical structure (according

to the Valence Bond theory) the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ double bonds are placed exocyclically with respect to the carbon pentagons (Taylor's rationale)¹⁹. Such double bond placement is shown in the [60]fullerene graph in Fig. 7. If now one X_2 molecule ($\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{F}, \text{Br}$) adds to a double bond then by simple numbering it is possible to show that there are eight different sites (double bonds) where the second X_2 molecule may add¹⁶. In Fig. 7 this has been shown by labeling the first $\text{C}=\text{C}$ by 0 and then the other possible sites by 1 to 8. Thus there are eight possible isomeric 1,2 addition products of formula C_{60}X_4 ; all of them has been predicted by theoretical computation²⁰ at the HF/6-31G* level and six C_{60}H_4 isomers have been experimentally isolated²¹.

Fig. 7. (a) Placement of double bonds exocyclically with respect to pentagons. (b) Labeling of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds for possible sites of attack in addition reactions of [60]fullerene to form isomeric C_{60}X_4 products.

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